

Examining The Knowledge Levels And Attitudes Towards Vaccinations Of Nurses Working At University Hospitals Regarding Biological Risks And Vaccinations

 Numan Mehmet KENGER¹, Kudret CİNVİZ¹, Sultan BAYAL¹, Elif ÖĞRETMEN¹, Suzan HAVLIOĞLU²

¹Nursing Student, Faculty of Health Sciences, Harran University, Sanliurfa, Türkiye

²Department of Public Health Nursing, Faculty of Health Sciences, Harran University, Sanliurfa, Türkiye

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Corresponding author: Numan Mehmet KENGER
E-mail: numanmehmetkenger@gmail.com

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ORCID ID

NMK: 0009-0007-2189-4372

KC: 0009-0006-6613-6690

SB: 0009-0002-9965-9317

EÖ: 0009-0003-3045-4767

SH: 0000-0001-5593-5688

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Biological hazards are the most significant factors putting healthcare workers at risk due to their working conditions and are also cited as the cause of many infectious diseases.

Objective: This study examined the knowledge and attitudes of nurses working in a university hospital regarding biological risks and the vaccinations required to protect against occupational infectious diseases.

Methods: The population of the descriptive study consisted of 524 nurses working at Harran University Faculty of Medicine Hospital, and the study was completed with 250 volunteer nurses between 01.09.2025 and 30.12.2025. Data were collected using a 20-question introductory information form prepared in line with the literature and through face-to-face interviews.

Results: 72.4% of nurses stated that they had received training on biological risks. When it came to protecting themselves against these risks, 89.2% cited the use of personal protective equipment and 76.4% cited hand hygiene as effective methods. In terms of vaccination status, 82.0% of nurses had received the hepatitis B vaccine, 26.4% the hepatitis A vaccine, 17.6% the chickenpox vaccine and 14.4% the seasonal influenza vaccine.

Conclusion: The study's findings suggest that, although nurses have some knowledge of biological risks, their understanding of and adherence to recommended vaccination and immunisation practices is inadequate. To protect healthcare workers against biological risks, it is recommended that regular in-service training is increased, vaccine tracking is carried out systematically, and information campaigns aimed at reducing vaccine hesitancy are planned.

Keywords: Biological Risk, Nurse, Occupational Infectious Diseases, Vaccination.

INTRODUCTION

The International Labour Organisation (ILO) and the World Health Organisation (WHO) define occupational health as the efforts made to maintain, sustain and improve the physical, mental and social well-being of workers in all occupations. Like all other sectors, the health sector involves certain specific risks (1). The risks that affect the biological, physical, chemical, ergonomic and psychosocial health of healthcare workers are classified into five groups. According to the US National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), healthcare workers in hospitals face 24 types of biological risk (2).

Biological hazards are the most significant factor putting healthcare workers at risk due to their working conditions, and they are also cited as the cause of many infectious diseases (3). In our country, six healthcare workers died as a result of needle stick injuries from Crimean-Congo Haemorrhagic Fever between 1998 and 2014 (4). It is also reported that healthcare workers are 3-10 times more at risk of tuberculosis, and that during the 2003 SARS outbreak in Canada, almost half of the cases occurred among healthcare workers (5). The recent pandemic has posed a threat to everyone, but has particularly affected healthcare workers. The International Council of Nurses has confirmed that 1,500 nurses from 44 countries have died from the virus (6). Studies clearly demonstrate that healthcare workers, especially nurses, are at a significantly higher risk of exposure to biological hazards.

Studies have shown that the most effective way to prevent healthcare workers from becoming ill is for them to understand the characteristics of infections, how they are transmitted and how to protect themselves against them, as well as being aware of their own immune status (7). Furthermore, taking personal precautions can reduce or eliminate the risk of contracting infectious diseases. This places certain responsibilities on employees and institutions. Essential measures for protecting healthcare workers from biological hazards include the use of personal protective equipment, vaccination, adherence to hygiene guidelines, appropriate climate control, waste segregation, safe injection practices, occupational health and safety, and health education (8).

In our country, there is also the Regulation on "Prevention of Risks from Exposure to Biological Factors" published in the Official Gazette No. 28678 dated June 15, 2013, by the Ministry of Labor and Social Security. This regulation consists of 21 articles and regulates the biological conditions of employees in the workplace and provides explanations about the types of occupational infectious diseases and methods of prevention. Article 16 of the regulation emphasizes that appropriate vaccinations against biological risks will be administered (9). The basic immunisation programme recommended by the US Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) for healthcare workers includes vaccines against influenza, measles, mumps, rubella (MMR), hepatitis B, tetanus, chickenpox, diphtheria and pertussis (Tdap) (10). In addition to these vaccines, there are also vaccines that are not included in the vaccination programme but are recommended by the CDC in specific circumstances (such as pneumococcal, meningococcal, hepatitis A, typhoid, polio, rabies, and BCG) (11).

Employers and managers are legally responsible for taking the necessary measures to eliminate or reduce occupational risks, i.e. for occupational health and safety (OHS) management. However, healthcare workers are also responsible for cooperating with management and taking measures to maintain health and wellbeing, and to prevent illness and accidents (12). Healthcare workers' ability to take responsibility for OHS is closely related to their ability to perceive risks in their working environment, classify risk levels (low, medium or high) and develop a protective and preventive attitude towards perceived risks (13).

Nurses are at high risk of transmitting infections because they provide direct care to patients at a distance of less than one metre. This study will evaluate nurses' knowledge and attitudes regarding biological risks and the vaccinations required to protect against occupational infectious diseases at the University Hospital.

METHODS

Population and Sample

This was a descriptive study. The study population consisted of 524 nurses working at Harran University Faculty of Medicine. The ideal sample size was calculated to be 222 using

the standard sampling calculation method, with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. The study was conducted between 01/09/2025 and 30/12/2025 and completed with the participation of 250 volunteer nurses.

Data Collection

After reviewing the literature, we created an introductory information form to collect the data (7,8,10,11). The researchers collected the research data using face-to-face interviews. Completion of the questionnaires took approximately 10–15 minutes.

Information Form

Nurses' personal characteristics (age, marital status) and professional characteristics (unit of employment, years of service in the profession), The status of vaccinations required for healthcare personnel, information on vaccinations against biological risks and occupational infectious diseases, vaccination levels and reasons for not getting vaccinated, and the status of pre-employment and periodic check-ups.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 26.0) software. Descriptive statistics (numbers, percentages and mean values) were used to evaluate the data from the study.

Ethical considerations

Permission to carry out the study has been obtained from the University's Clinical Research Ethics Committee (decision no. 12.05.2025/09), the University Rectorate Hospital Chief Medical Officer and the individuals participating in the study. The study was supported under the 2209-A University Student Research Projects Support Programme.

RESULTS

Of the nurses participating in the study, 57.2% were female, 53.6% were aged 19-30, 70.4% were married, and 54.8% had a bachelor's degree. 33.6% had 10 years or more of experience, and 51.6% worked in intensive care units (Table 1).

Table 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of Nurses Participating in the Study

Variables		Number	Percentage
Gender	Woman	143	57.2
	Man	107	42.8
Age	19-30	134	53.6
	31-59	116	46.4
Marital Status	Married	176	70.4
	Single	74	29.6
Education	Health college	20	8.0
	Undergraduate degree	74	29.6
	Bachelor's degree	137	54.8
	Master's degree	19	7.6
Professional Experience	1 - 5 year	77	30.8
	6 - 10 year	89	35.6
	10 - 30 year	84	33.6
Department Worked In	Inpatient services	49	19.6
	Surgical services	55	22.0
	Intensive care	129	51.6
	Operating theatre	14	5.6
	Administrative	3	1.2
Do you have any diagnosed health problems?	Yes	43	17.2
	No	207	82.8

Of the nurses participating in the study, 72.4% stated that they had received training on biological risks. Of these nurses, 52.8% stated that there was a biological risk factor in their work environment that they believed negatively affected their health. Of these nurses, 83.2% stated that the biological risk in their workplace

was viruses and 74.4% stated that it was bacteria. Table 2 shows that 89.2% of nurses believe that biological risks can be prevented by using personal protective equipment such as masks, gloves and gowns, and 76.4% believe that frequent hand washing is effective (Table 2).

Table 2. Nurses' knowledge and attitudes regarding biological hazards

Variables		Number	Percentage
You have received training on biological risks	Yes	181	72.4
	No	69	27.6
What biological risks might exist in your workplace	Virus	208	83.2
	Bacteria	186	74.4
	Fungus	116	46.4
	Parasite	99	39.6
Are there any biological risk factors in your working environment that you believe could adversely affect your health?	Present	132	52.8
	Absent	66	26.4
	I don't know	52	20.8
How can you protect yourself from biological risks?	Wear personal protective equipment (apron/mask/gloves)	223	89.2
	Get vaccinated	129	51.6
	Use disinfectant	169	67.6
	Washing your hands frequently	191	76.4
	Following hygiene rules	185	74.0
	It is impossible to protect yourself	20	8.0
	I don't know	3	1.2
	Other		

90.0% of the nurses participating in the study stated that they had undergone a pre-employment medical examination. Of these nurses, 94.4% stated that they had undergone further testing upon starting work, with 82.8%

of these tests being hepatitis marker tests and 81.6% being blood count tests (Table 3).

Table 3. Pre-employment Medical Examination Status of Nurses Participating in the Study

Variables		Number	Percentage
Was a pre-employment medical examination conducted?	Yes	225	90.0
	No	25	10.0
Did you undergo any medical tests when you started work?	Yes	236	94.4
	No	14	5.6
If yes, which ones were examined?	Blood count	204	81.6
	Urine analysis	68	27.2
	Chest X-ray	202	80.8
	Blood biochemistry	180	72.0
	Hepatitis markers	207	82.8
	PPD test	53	21.2
	HIV	101	40.4
Are periodic medical examinations conducted?	Never done	19	7.6
	Once a year	184	73.6
	Every six months	47	18.8

Of the nurses participating in the study, 91.2% responded that the vaccines that must be administered to healthcare workers are Hepatitis B, and 77.6% responded that the vaccines that must be administered in special circumstances are Hepatitis B. 82.0% of the

nurses stated that they had received the Hepatitis B vaccine and 26.4% the Hepatitis A vaccine, and 39.2% stated that they had not received all 5 vaccines that healthcare workers are required to have due to complications that the vaccine might cause (Table 4).

Table 4. Nurses' knowledge and attitudes regarding vaccinations

Variables		Number	Percentage
Which vaccinations do you think healthcare workers must receive?	Hepatitis B	228	91.2
	Hepatitis A	130	52.0
	Seasonal Influenza	77	30.8
	MMR	47	18.8
	Chickenpox	41	16.4
	Tdap	40	16.0
	Pneumococcal	37	14.8
	Meningococcal	37	14.8
	Whooping cough	32	12.8
	Rabies	28	11.2
	Typhoid	26	10.4
Which vaccines can be administered to healthcare workers in special circumstances?	Polio	22	8.8
	Hepatitis B	194	77.6
	Hepatitis A	100	40.0
	Seasonal Influenza	63	25.2
	Rabies	60	24.0
	Meningococcal	40	16.8
	Pneumococcal	40	16.0
	Chickenpox	32	12.8
	Whooping cough	27	10.8
	Tdap	25	10.0
	Typhoid	23	9.2
Which of the following vaccines have you had?	MMR	22	8.8
	Polio	14	5.6
	Hepatitis B	205	82.0
	Hepatitis A	66	26.4
	Chickenpox	44	17.6
	Seasonal Influenza	36	14.4
	MMR	35	14.0
	Tdap	27	10.8
	Whooping cough	20	8.0
	Polio	14	5.6
	Rabies	14	5.6
What are your reasons for not having all five vaccines that healthcare workers should have?	Typhoid	11	4.4
	Meningococcal	9	3.6
	Pneumococcal	8	3.2
	Complications that may be caused by the vaccine	98	39.2
	Distrust of vaccines	94	37.6
	Lack of information	81	32.4
	Personal beliefs	17	6.8
	Other	47	18.8

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to reveal the knowledge and attitudes of nurses working in a university hospital regarding biological risks and immunisation against occupational infectious diseases. While the nurses were able to define biological risks broadly, there were significant gaps in their knowledge of prevention methods, particularly with regard to the scope and application levels of recommended vaccines.

While it is positive that 72.4% of nurses reported receiving training on biological risks,

this figure is lower than that reported in some previous studies. For instance, Gülen et al. (2025) found that over 95% of nurses had received institution-based training (14). This discrepancy could be attributed to differences in institutions' occupational health and safety policies, the frequency of in-service training, and the standardisation of training content. Indeed, reports published by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Labour Organization (ILO) emphasize that regular and sustainable training programmes for healthcare workers are a fundamental strategy for preventing occupational infections (15). In

this context, the rate identified in the present study shows that training programmes are in place, but suggests that their content and effectiveness need to be reviewed.

The fact that the vast majority of participants cited viruses and bacteria as biological risk factors suggests a basic awareness of infectious agents. However, the lower rates at which other biological agents, such as fungi and parasites, were mentioned suggest that risk perception is shaped by frequently encountered, high-profile infections. This can particularly be explained by the impact of pandemic processes on risk perception. Furthermore, the fact that nurses most frequently mention personal protective equipment (PPE) and hand hygiene as protective measures suggests that they are familiar with standard infection control measures. However, the literature reports that there is not always a correlation between knowledge and practice. Review studies by Demiralp (2023) and Moanazara et al. suggest that nurses' knowledge and practice regarding PPE use and hand hygiene is deficient (16,17). Further research is therefore needed to examine the extent to which the high rates reported in the current study are reflected in behaviour.

The findings regarding vaccination status are noteworthy. The fact that 82% of participants had received the hepatitis B vaccine is positive news for nurses, who are at high risk of coming into contact with blood and bodily fluids. However, the rates of other recommended vaccinations, such as those for hepatitis A, chickenpox, measles, mumps and rubella (MMR), tetanus, diphtheria and pertussis (Tdap), and seasonal influenza, were found to be significantly low. These findings are consistent with national and international studies. A study conducted by Maltezou et al. (2022) in Greece also reported low immunisation rates for many vaccines (18). In India, Batra et al. (2015) reported full-dose Hepatitis B vaccination rates of between 16% and 60% (19). A study conducted by Küçük et al. (2024) in Turkey also indicated that healthcare workers' completion rates for all recommended vaccines were low (20). These results demonstrate that vaccination rates among healthcare workers remain low.

Recommendations for the vaccination of healthcare workers have been defined by organisations such as the Centers for Disease

Control and Prevention, and include vaccines such as those for influenza, MMR, hepatitis B, Tdap and chickenpox. Furthermore, Regulation 15/06/2013 on the prevention of exposure risks to biological agents explicitly states that employers in our country must provide appropriate vaccinations for their employees. However, the low vaccination rates identified in the current study suggest that there may be a discrepancy between legislation and practice.

Examining the reasons nurses gave for not getting vaccinated revealed that the most frequently reported reasons were possible complications of the vaccine (39.2%), distrust of vaccines (37.6%), and lack of information (32.4%). These findings are consistent with the concept of 'vaccine hesitancy', as defined in the literature. Studies by Galanakis et al. (2013) and Khubchandani et al. (2022) have also reported that concerns and misconceptions about vaccine safety among healthcare workers have a negative effect on vaccination rates (21-22). As healthcare workers are role models for the community, this hesitancy may have individual and societal consequences.

Limitations of The Study

This study has certain limitations. Firstly, the fact that the research was conducted at a single centre limits the generalisability of the findings. Furthermore, collecting data through self-reporting methods may have introduced respondent bias. Nevertheless, the study provides valuable insights into the current situation regarding biological risks and vaccination among nurses working in university hospitals.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, while nurses have a basic awareness of biological risks, their knowledge and practice levels regarding recommended vaccinations and immunisation procedures are inadequate. In this regard, it is recommended that the content and frequency of in-service training are increased, that occupational health units actively monitor vaccinations and that evidence-based information programmes on vaccine safety are implemented. Protecting healthcare workers is critical to patient safety, the quality of care and the sustainability of healthcare systems.

DESCRIPTIONS

No conflict of interest.

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